

**AGNIKARMA IN GRANTHI (SEBACEOUS CYST) OVER KARNAPALI: A SINGLE
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ABSTRACT

In Ayurveda, Granthi is attributed to vitiated Kapha dosha. It can be correlated with Medoja Granthi, characterized by symptoms such as being snigdha (unctuous), mrudu (soft), chala (movable), having sita-asita strava (discharge), tvaka savarna (skin-colored), and niruja shotha (painless swelling). In modern science, this can be correlated with a sebaceous cyst. According to Acharya Sushruta, Granthi roga can be treated by Agnikarma (Su. Su. 12/10). Acharya Sushruta also states that Agnikarma is a superior parasurgical procedure in Ayurveda, as diseases treated by it usually do not relapse (Su. Su. 12/3). A 54-year-old male patient visited the outpatient department of Panchakarma with a 2-3 year history of a non-inflammatory cystic swelling over the left earlobe. The patient had taken some oral medications and local applications 2 years ago but did not experience any effect. Concerned about cosmetic appearance, the patient consulted an Ayurvedic hospital for better management. Agnikarma, a superior parasurgical procedure for Kapha dosha-related diseases, was performed to remove the Granthi. After treatment, the cyst was completely cured without any scarring after 6 weeks. The patient had no recurrence. This case demonstrates the advantages of Agnikarma in treating Granthi.

KEYWORDS: Sebaceous cyst, Granthi roga, Agnikarma, Thermal cautery.**INTRODUCTION**

In Ayurveda, Granthi is attributed to vitiated Kapha dosha. Granthi manifests as a tubercle-like swelling of the skin when vitiated Vatadi doshas further vitiate the Mamsa, Rakta, Kapha, and Meda dhatus. Sebaceous cysts, which correlate with Granthi in Ayurveda, are small, slow-growing, non-cancerous elevations on the skin. They are smooth to touch, vary in size, are round in shape, a dark dot (punctum) in centre and are most commonly found on the face, neck, back, and hairy areas. While sebaceous cysts often don't need treatment, they can cause discomfort, especially cosmetically. Removal is considered if the cyst is painful, infected, or if appearance is a concern.

According to Acharya Sushruta in Ayurveda, Agnikarma (thermal cautery) is a superior parasurgical procedure for treating Granthi roga with minimal risk of relapse (Su. Su. 12/10). Agnikarma is noted for its ability to cure

diseases not treatable by Shastra, Kshar, or Bhesaj, and it has the property to destroy pathology in deeper structures. Causes of sebaceous cysts include skin trauma, blocked ducts, acne, hormonal changes, and excess sebum production. Agnikarma can be used for excision. Given this is a single case report, further trials with a larger sample size are needed for scientific validation.

CASE REPORT

Name of patient- ABC

Age/sex-54 yr/ Male

Opd no- 2022MR04598

Place-Mankhurd

Occupation- Farmer

Date of consultantion- 28/11/2024.

Chief complaints

cystic swelling over left ear lobe since 2-3 years.

Present and past History

No H/o -HTN/DM/KOCH'S
No any surgical history
No any history of addiction.

Examination of cyst

Inspection- Position over left earlobe
Initial Palpation- pulsation-Not present
Tenderness- Not present
Palpation- Mobility- Freely mobile
Shape -Round
Surface- smooth
Appearance- a dark dot (punctum) in its centre
Consistency- Uniform all over
Fluctuation-present
Temperature-same as whole body
On the basis of clinical examination it was diagnosed sebaceous cyst.

Investigations

CBC, BSL- fasting PP, BT, CT.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material- Cotton, Gauze pieces, Icepack, Gloves, Tamra Shalaka, Ghee (Shatdhauta), Aloe vera leaf, stove.

Procedure

- Written informed consent had been taken from the patient.
- First of all patient kept in right lateral position.
- Aloe vera gel applied around and cyst site.
- Tamra shalaka was heated on the stove, after shalaka got red hot it was applied at the base of cyst. It was repeated upto complete excision of cyst.
- After excision samyak dagdha was done over cyst excision Site to avoid relapse of cyst.
- After that shatdhaut ghrit was applied over.

RESULT

Cyst completely cured without any oral medicine, anesthesia and surgical procedure. No any scar, no any recurrence and safest method.

DISCUSSION

The patient was cured after a single sitting of Agnikarma without any complications such as burning sensation, scarring, etc. Agnikarma is a parasurgical procedure indicated for Vataja-Kaphaja Vyadhi. It has the properties of being Ushna (hot), Tikshna (sharp), Sukshma (subtle), Vyavayi (pervasive), Vikasi (spreading), and Pachana (digesting). These properties enable Agnikarma to destroy pathology in deeper structures, thereby helping to pacify vitiated Vata and Kapha doshas and relieve diseases caused by them.

Acharya Sushruta stated that diseases not cured by Bhesaj (medicines), Kshara (alkalis), or Sastra (surgical) treatments can be cured by Agnikarma. Moreover, due to its sterile nature, there is minimal chance of disease recurrence.

Before agnikarma

After agnikarma on same day

After 6 weeks

CONCLUSION

Based on this case, it can be concluded that Agnikarma can be performed to treat sebaceous cysts. Agnikarma is an effective procedure with minimal risk of bleeding or recurrence. Since there is no scarring or other complications after healing, Agnikarma can also be considered for cosmetic purposes.

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